

THEORETICAL BASIS OF DESIGN IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

¹Ibraimov Kholboy, ²I.N.Navruzov

¹Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kari
Niyazi, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²Independent researcher of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022721>

Abstract. *This article presents the theoretical foundations of the design of the educational process today, the history of the design method and various opinions of European scientists, as well as the types of the design method and the stages of project selection.*

Keywords: *project, game project, excursion projects, narrative projects, device projects, design.*

Humanization and democratization of teacher-pupil relations, respect for the learner's personality, and the person-oriented model of education based on consideration of his interests and needs have been widely implemented in our republic. As a result, it was possible to develop qualities such as free, independent thinking, conscious attitude to the surrounding reality, involvement and social activity in students. In our country, "continue to further improve the continuous education system, increase opportunities for quality education services, train highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" [1; 74-b], physically healthy, mentally and intellectually developed, independent-thinking, with a firm outlook on life, raising young people loyal to the Motherland, deepening democratic reforms and increasing their social activity in the process of developing civil society takes an important place.

In all times, humanity has set itself the goal of educating the young generation to be mature in all respects, spiritually mature, with solid knowledge and potential. To achieve this noble goal, he used various methods and methods, and tried to increase the effectiveness of education.

On the basis of pedagogical ideas in the history of Europe, the great scientists who have been carrying out the education and training of the population for nearly 300 years and their ideas were the basis for the creation of the pedagogical technology method. developed by the famous educator John Dewey and his follower William Kilpatrick. Currently, project-based teaching is widely used in schools in the USA and other countries. For the first time, the idea of cooperative education appeared in the works of American educational researchers E.Parkhurst, J.Devey, and U.H.Kilpatrick "Project method" at the beginning of the 20th century. This method began to form in the USA in 1919. A. Bine in France, V.A.Lag, E.Meyman in Germany, E.Claparel in Switzerland, O.Decrole in Belgium, E.Thorndike in the USA and others conducted independent research.

Designing the educational process was first applied to the educational process in American schools at the beginning of the 20th century. The American professor U.H.Kilpatrick worked as a professor at the University of Chicago since 1896 and established an "Experimental School-Laboratory" in front of the university. Another pedagogue, J.Collings, in the 1910s conducted a long-term experimental test of the design of the educational process in one of the rural schools of the state of Missouri. He was the first in the world to categorize the design of the educational process and divided his projects into four groups:

"Games project" is a children's activity, the main goal of which is to participate in group activities, including various games, folk dances, drama productions, various entertainments, etc.

"Excursion projects" - in these projects, it is intended to study the problems related to the environment and community life.

"Storytelling projects" are designed for children to "enjoy stories in different forms" - oral, written, song, poem, artistic (picture - image), musical (playing musical instruments), etc. .

"Device projects" are aimed at creating a specific useful product: making traps for rabbits and birds, building a stage for a school theater, making pots for flowers, etc.

Project is derived from the Latin word "project" which means "projectus", "put forward", "prominent", "pronounced". In fact, during the planning of the project, the teacher looks into the future, imagines something, and the student creates or imagines something by spending a certain amount of time and effort.

The term "planning" entered pedagogy from the field of technology and means planning [2;]. The need to design the pedagogical process depends on the complexity of the educational content.

Designing in education is a special (laboratory) that ensures the student's independent action by the teacher from searching for a problem, planning and organizing activities to solve it, to presenting a solution method (intellectual or material product) for public evaluation. conditions) is an organized purposeful educational activity

Projects can be given as follows. In this:

- projects that include planning and preparation of a device or mechanism;
- projects designed to improve development processes.
- adoption of modern methods and improved technology through their implementation - projects aimed at achieving high results and increasing labor efficiency;
- projects to research a new approach, method or tool.

Such projects use local materials and also solve some local problems:

- preparation of plans, designs and working drawings and estimates;
- prevention of negative changes in the production process of materials.

Some projects focus on the production of a prototype of a state-of-the-art device, taking into account all aspects from start to finish. It is necessary that the project should always be focused on a real-life situation, meet some needs of the society, and students should participate in its adoption [4;].

The selection of the project is based on the surrounding areas and their needs. determines whether This does not allow the teacher to order supplies in advance and does not guarantee that all tasks will be completed. Rather, it encourages students to take responsibility for their learning and allows them to choose projects that ensure they meet their needs and learning goals. A well-chosen project allows to work based on knowledge and skills, especially to achieve the set goal and implement the result.

The project must include the application of knowledge, intellectual abilities and skills, be understandable, be properly distributed in terms of the cost and time of the necessary materials, be suitable for the level of knowledge, ability and ability of the student, from the level of their ability. ensures that it is not high.

Stages of project selection:

- 1) setting the problem;

- 2) determination of goals and tasks aimed at solving the problem;
- 3) proposal of alternative decisions;
- 4) selection of the best decision;
- 5) perform detailed design taking into account costs;
- 6) preparation and assembly of components;
- 7) conducting a test and evaluation to find a solution to the initially accepted task;
- 8) preparation of the project report.

In project planning, the student selects a project that meets the learning objectives and then develops a project plan. This plan includes: an image or sketch of the project; available information sources; equipment, materials and expenses necessary for the implementation of the project, as well as cost estimates; technological map of project execution; project evaluation criteria.

Teacher's role. The teacher-student relationship is collaborative and informal, different from the normal teaching process in the classroom, which helps the students to freely choose the project according to their capabilities. The teacher is required to act as a leader throughout the project and guide students to complete the project and encourage them to think independently. This method supports labor achievements. It develops students' independence, sense of responsibility and creativity, and builds determination in solving practical tasks.

In the process of working on the project, students learn to draw conclusions and write reports about the accumulated experience. They, in turn, form knowledge, skills and qualifications, and inspire a sense of motivation for further creative and scientific work in life. The use of the projecting method in education serves to organize the educational process of future teachers, to develop the thinking of students, and to know in advance the results that will be achieved during the lesson. As a result, the quality and efficiency of teaching will increase, and the professional competence of students will be formed.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov I.A. Xavfsizlik va barqaror taraqqiyot yo'lida. -T: "O'zbekiston", 1998. B.400.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Qonun ustivorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash-yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligining garovi. –T.: O'zbekiston, 2017. –B. 22.
3. Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2001). *Research Methods in Education*. 5th Edition, Routledge Falmer: London.
4. Давыдов В.В. Теория развивающего обучения. – М.: «Интор», 1996.–542 с.
5. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // *Science, education and culture*. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
6. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan // *Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal*. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
7. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education* 1 (2020): 6-15.
8. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
9. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., "Shaffof", 2023, 416-bet.

10. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
11. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
12. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
13. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
14. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
15. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).